

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS DURING UNIVERSITY STUDIES

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Abstract. *Physical culture in a higher educational institution is an integral part of the formation of the general and professional culture of the personality of a modern person, and is also an integral part of the system of humanistic education of students. As an academic discipline required for all specialties, it is one of the means of forming a comprehensively developed personality, optimizing the physical and psycho-physiological state of students in the process of professional training.*

Keywords: *physical culture, sports, physical education, physical development, professional orientation of physical education, higher education institution.*

INTRODUCTION

The educational activities of a higher educational institution are based on the systematic nature of education and upbringing, as well as the professional training of specialists; in this process, the formation of a worldview, socio-political, labor, moral, physical, aesthetic and other types of education organically merge [1, p. 56].

At present, humanistic educational systems have developed and continue to develop in higher educational institutions. At the same time, each general education system should give due place to both physical education and sports. All this is necessary to establish balance and strengthen the relationships between the constituent elements of education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Physical education and, in particular, sports are an effective method of organizing students' leisure time. No other social sphere of leisure activities attracts such a huge number of people (billions of people watch the Olympic Games on television).

In this case, we can talk about the mass character of sports and physical culture.

The goal of physical education in a higher educational institution is to realize the possibilities of optimal physical development of students, comprehensive improvement of physical qualities and related abilities in conjunction with the education of spiritual and moral qualities that characterize a socially active and highly moral personality: to ensure on this basis the preparedness of each student for productive labor and other important activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let's consider more specific tasks that contribute to the formation of this goal. They are usually divided into two groups: specific and general pedagogical. [1, p. 3].

1) Specific ones are also divided into groups:

1) tasks to optimize the physical development of students in the direction of not only the comprehensive development of their inherent physical qualities, improving motor abilities, strengthening, but also long-term health preservation.

“Physical qualities” of a student are usually called the innate qualities that make physical activity possible (muscle mass, speed, endurance, flexibility, etc.). The basis of this diversity of a

student's abilities is the totality of those natural qualities of his, thanks to which he can show strength, speed and power in movements, and perform prolonged physical work, despite the fatigue that has arisen. The level of development of these qualities determines how much a person is able to carry out physical activity. The tasks of guaranteeing health are solved on the basis of instilling physical qualities characteristic of each person, the development of which leads to an increase in the overall level of endurance, as well as the functional and adaptive capabilities of the body.

2) Basic ones are special educational tasks. The main ones are 1) to enlighten each student with basic knowledge of a scientific and practical nature acquired in the field of physical education.; 2) to ensure the rational formation of individual motor skills and abilities necessary in the process of individual development, and to improve them as much as possible.

The significance of these tasks is due to the fact that without motor skills and abilities it is impossible to realize abilities in practical activities.

These two groups of specific tasks are closely interrelated, but are not reducible to each other either logically or in their practical implementation. They need to be differentiated, but at the same time we must keep in mind the organic interconnectedness and interdependence of the results of the implementation of these tasks.

2) General pedagogical. The most important of them in the education system are tasks that provide for the moral and labor education of the student, as well as tasks for cultivating will, empathy, positive character traits and aesthetic needs of the individual. The unity of human physical and spiritual development effectively allows us to solve these problems.

Physical culture in a higher educational institution, as a subject of knowledge, has a complex structure; it includes the impact on various systems of the body of students, improvement of physical and moral-volitional qualities and psychological stability, on the neuro-emotional mental sphere of students. [3, p. 56].

It is a process of uniform, systematic influence on students under the responsible and sensitive supervision and guidance of teachers, who are designed to instill knowledge in future specialists and form in them a clear understanding of the social significance of physical culture and sports in the conditions of production activities and on the basis of forming a stable personality in every sense.

The process of physical education is not realized on its own if the teaching process is not organized accordingly.

Massive studies of student youth indicate that, along with students who are truly interested and regularly involved in physical education and sports, there is also a significant portion of students who are not interested in this area in their life.

Physical education as an academic discipline in a higher educational institution is significantly different in content, structure, organization and conduct of classes from physical education lessons in primary and secondary schools.

The result of training should be the creation of sustainable motivation and the need for a healthy and productive lifestyle, physical self-improvement, and achieving the maximum level of physical fitness.

Distinctive features of the curriculum are its broad general educational focus, the presence of methodological and practical classes and final certification.

The professional orientation of the educational process in physical culture is included in all sections of the program, playing a connecting, coordinating and activating role.

The need for further development of physical culture and sports among students is determined by the needs and personal rights of young people, age-related and individual characteristics of their development, constantly changing living conditions, and the “social order” of society for the training of highly qualified specialists.

This order presupposes that future specialists must have general and professional culture, physical and mental health, high performance, and the ability to master and enrich the cultural potential of society.

Forms of physical education of students: physical education at a university is carried out throughout the entire period of students’ education and is carried out in diverse forms that are interconnected, complement each other and represent a single process of physical education of students. Classes are the main form of physical education in higher education institutions. They are planned in the curricula for all specialties, and their implementation is ensured by teachers of the departments of physical education. Students’ independent studies in physical culture, sports, and tourism contribute to better assimilation of educational material, allow them to increase the total time of physical exercise, accelerate the process of physical improvement, and are one of the ways to introduce physical culture and sports into the life and recreation of students. In conjunction with educational activities, properly organized independent activities ensure optimal continuity and effectiveness of physical education. These classes can be conducted outside of class time on the instructions of teachers or in sections [3].

CONCLUSION

The basis for the specificity of its functions is that it arose, developed and is developing as a competitive activity. This implies, first of all, the importance of sport as a kind of standard for assessing human capabilities, i.e. Specific competitive-reference function of sport. This function is most clearly expressed in elite sports, where sporting achievements of a universal human scale are established and exceeded. But to one degree or another, it is also characteristic of sports in general.

To the same extent, sport also has a specific empirical-achievement function, which lies in the fact that it represents a special type of search activity associated with a person’s knowledge of his capabilities together with the search for effective ways to maximize, increase and optimize them.

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